

(1)

(5)

(6)

for M^+CO , M^+CH_3CN and M^+HCN clearly indicated that the breakdown did not initiate from the pyrimidine part of the quinazolone ring. The presence of peaks for M^+H , M^+CH_3 , M^+O , M^+H-O , M^+NO , M^+NO_2 and M^+H-NO_2 in these compounds clearly revealed that the substituents at positions 6 and 7 participated in the breakdown of these compounds. Compound 6 disappeared immediately under the conditions used for compounds 2-5, in the mass spectrometer and so had to be recorded at lower probe temperature. The observed peaks, however, supported the aforementioned behaviour reported for 2-5. Computer print out of 1, 5 and 6 along with their percentage abundance is presented for the sake of clarity. The preparation of the compounds studied have been reported earlier⁵.

References

1. T. J. BALTERHAM, A. C. K. TRIFFETT and J. A. WUNDERLICH, *J. Chem. Soc. B*, 1967, 892
2. M. LUCKNER, K. WINTER and L. NOVER, *Tetrahedron*, 1969, 25, 2575
3. R. R. PRADT, S. H. EGGERS and A. JORDAAN, *Tetrahedron*, 1967, 23, 3521.
4. R. M. SILVERSTEIN, G. C. BASSLER and T. C. MORRILL, "Spectrometric identification of organic compounds", New York, 1974, p. 33.
5. J. ROY, M. SETH and A. P. BHADURI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1978, 16, 42.

¹³C Nmr Study of 5-Aryl-4-(3-methyl-5-styryl-4-isoxazolyl)-3-phenyl- Δ^2 -1,2,4-oxadiazolines

E RAJANARENDAR, C. JANAKIRAM RAO
and
A KRISHNA MURTHY*

Department of Chemistry, Kakatiya University,
Warangal-506 009

Manuscript received 11 April 1985, accepted 24 December 1985

THE synthesis and mass spectral behaviour¹ of 5-aryl-4-(3-methyl-5-styryl-4-isoxazolyl)-3-phenyl- Δ^2 -1,2,4-oxadiazolines have been reported from these laboratories. ¹³C nmr spectra of these compounds is discussed in this paper and this happens to be the first ever report on ¹³C nmr data of isoxazolyloxadiazolines. ¹³C nmr study of isoxazoloazepines has earlier been reported by us².

The chemical shift values of the various carbons of five isoxazolyloxadiazolines (1-5) studied, have been presented in Table 1. The assignments are based on chemical shifts, off-resonance multiplicities and internal consistency. In the spectrum of 3,5-diphenyl-4-isoxazolyloxadiazoline (1) with wide-band proton decoupling sixteen lines have been

listed in the computer printout of line frequencies. An off-resonance single frequency decoupling experiment showed that the multiplicities of these lines due to proton decoupling correspond to seven singlets (quaternary carbons), eight doublets (CH carbons), and one quarter (CH_2). The fifteen aromatic CH of the three benzene rings come as five doublets.

(1)

- (2) 4''-Cl
 (3) 4''-OCH₃
 (4) 4''-CH₃
 (5) 3''-OCH₃, 4''-OH

The broadening of the methyl peak found in the range δ 9.0-10.8 ppm is most probably, due to coupling to ^{14}N nuclei. The signal which falls in the range 99.5-99.85 in all the compounds is assignable to the tertiary carbon atom of the oxadiazoline ring^a. The two ethylenic carbons α and β resonate at 110 and 115, respectively. Carbon- β is more deshielded than carbon- α as it experiences the mesomeric withdrawal of electrons by the isoxazole ring $\text{C}=\text{N}$ and hence resonates at lower field^a. The absorption due to C'_4 , which is part of the chromophore encompassing the isoxazole-ring double

TABLE I— ^{13}C NMR CHEMICAL SHIFTS (δ) OF ISOXAZOLYLOXADIAZOLINES (1-5)^a

Carbons	1	2	3	4	5
CH_3 (q)	9.00	10.65	9.63	9.45	9.18
3 (s)	161.20	161.25	161.00	161.29	161.50
5 (d)	99.70	98.29	99.85	99.69	98.50
α (d)	109.87	109.67	110.24	110.01	110.36
β (d)	115.20	115.73	114.32	111.60	115.62
3' (s)	155.50	155.35	155.00	155.72	155.11
4' (s)	135.50	136.00	135.80	135.00	135.42
5' (s)	158.00	158.52	158.05	158.93	158.45
Miscellaneous ^b	—	—	55.29	21.01	55.75
	—	134.20	(q, OMe)	(q, CH ₃)	(q, OMe)
	—	(s, 4'')	159.40	136.50	157.05
	—	—	(s, 4'')	(s, 4'')	(s, 3'')
	—	—	—	—	160.25
	—	—	—	—	(s, 4'')

^aOff-resonance multiplicities in parenthesis. ^bIncludes substituents on benzene ring in compounds 2-5.

bonds and styryl moiety, is at 135.5, found in all the compounds. The peak at 158 is due to C'_5 , which is flanked by ethylenic double bond and isoxazole ring oxygen. Assigning such a downfield absorption to this carbon is justified because it is also under the electron withdrawing influence of $\text{C}=\text{N}$ of the isoxazole. All the five compounds

show signal around 155 assignable, most probably, to C'_4 . The most downfield signal of the spectrum at 161.30 is due to C_3 , as it is an sp^3 carbon attached to two nitrogens in addition to a benzene ring.

The rest of the assignments are complicated by the presence of three aromatic rings which result in strong signals near 128 ppm which are not readily distinguished from one another.

Experimental

Instrument : Nucleus, ^{13}C ; frequency, 20 MHz, instrument, Varian FT-80A; mode, FT; lock, internal; temperature, 30°; solvent, (a) compounds 1-4 in CDCl_3 and (b) compound 5 in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$; concentration, 0.5 M; tube size, 10 mm o.d.; standard, TMS; pulse width, 5 μs ; acquisition time, 1.0 s; spectral width, 5 KHz; number of transients, 80 000 and 110 000; number of data point, 10 000, decoupling conditions, decoupling mode (1), decoupler off set (56); flip angle, 45°; repetition rate 1.0 s; digital resolution, 1.6 points/Hz; and resolution enhancement, sensitivity enhancement was employed, using a decreasing exponential weighting function with a time constant of 0.7 Hz, resulting in 0.45 Hz line broadening

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Prof. E. V. Sundaram, Head, Department of Chemistry and Dean, Faculty of Science, Kakatiya University, Warangal, for facilities and Dr. J. N. Shoolery for the spectra.

References

1. E. RAJANARENDAR, C. J. RAO and A. K. MURTHY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1981, 20, 839.
2. C. J. RAO, A. K. MURTHY and J. N. SHOOLERY, *Org. Magn. Reson.*, 1983, 21, 77.
3. E. RAJANARENDAR, Ph D Thesis, Kakatiya University, Warangal, 1982, p. 55.

Synthesis of 2-Aryl-4(1H)-anthryridinones

K. MOGILAI AH, K. RAJENDAR REDDY,
K. VIJAYENDER REDDY and B. SREENIVASULU*

Department of Chemistry, Kakatiya University,
Warangal-506 009

Manuscript received 4 July 1985 accepted 24 December 1985

SCANTY information is available in literature concerning the chemistry of anthryridines¹⁻⁴. In the present communication, a series of hitherto unknown 2-aryl-4(1H)-anthryridinones are reported

Scheme 1